

Enhanced Photocatalytic Hydrogen Production on TiO₂ by Using Carbon Materials

Authors : Bashir Ahmmad, Kensaku Kanomata, Fumihiko Hirose

Abstract : The effect of carbon materials on TiO₂ for the photocatalytic hydrogen gas production from water/alcohol mixtures was investigated. Single walled carbon nanotubes (SWNTs), multi walled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs), carbon nanofiber (CNF), fullerene (FLN), graphite (GP), and graphite silica (GS) were used as co-catalysts by directly mixing with TiO₂. Drastic synergy effects were found with increase in the amount of hydrogen gas by a factor of ca. 150 and 100 for SWNTs and GS with TiO₂, respectively. The order of H₂ gas production for these carbon materials was SWNTs > GS >> MWNTs > FLN > CNF > GP. To maximize the hydrogen production from SWNTs/TiO₂, various parameters of experimental conditions were changed. Also, a comparison between Pt/TiO₂, WNTs/TiO₂ and GS/TiO₂ was made for the amount of H₂ gas production. Finally, the recyclability of SWNTs/TiO₂ and GS/TiO₂ were tested.

Keywords : photocatalysis, carbon materials, alcohol reforming, hydrogen production, titanium oxide

Conference Title : ICEEPE 2014 : International Conference on Electrical, Electronics and Power Engineering

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : January 20-21, 2014